

DIMENSIONS AND STRATEGIES ON KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND THE ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN LUCENA WEST DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

A smarter workforce ensures that all members have access to the organization's overall experience and can make instant, informed decisions that benefit the group. Internally, innovation is more easily promoted, teachers, benefit from better access to best practices, and worker turnover is reduced. Thus, dimensions and strategies of knowledge management need to be addressed from different schools leading the school towards a better organization. This study focused on the dimensions and strategies of knowledge management and the organizational development of public elementary schools in Lucena West District. This study utilized a descriptive and correlational type of research. The respondents of this study were 169 elementary teachers who are currently employed in eleven (11) schools of Lucena West District, Division of Lucena City. The data gathered indicated that in terms of technology and support, acquisition and learning, dissemination of information, applying knowledge, and teacher competency teachers practiced these to a great extent. In the strategies of knowledge management, learner's information system, human resources and, role delegation data revealed that teachers agreed that strategies of knowledge management aim to develop the organization. Moreover, vision and mission, organizational structure, governance, stakeholder's engagement and retention, and technology and infrastructure teachers developed these to a great extent. The findings revealed that dimensions and strategies of knowledge management have a significant relationship to organizational development. Dimensions and strategies of knowledge management and organizational development are significantly related to each other. After numerous statistical treatments, we can draw that there is a high correlation between dimensions and strategies on knowledge management and the organizational development in public elementary schools in Lucena West District. The study suggests that the use of dimensions and strategies on knowledge management and organizational development supports a positive significant increase in the betterment of the school's system.

Keywords: mode of learning, transactional distance learning, modular distance learning, online survey, online interview